

A Review of Avocado Waste Valorization and Integrated Biorefinery System

Introduction

Avocado is grown in many different parts of the world and is one of the most widely produced and consumed fruit globally (Rodriguez-Martinez et al., 2022; Garcia-Vargas et al., 2020). In recent years, there have been steady increase in global production of avocado and ditto for consumption as well. There was a 13.9% increase in global production between 2019 and 2020 (Rodriguez-Martinez et al., 2022), and with a total global production of about 8.69 million tons in 2021 (Statista, 2023). The demand for avocado is being driven by its nutritional and health benefits. It consists about 72% of water, low in sugar and rich source of dietary fibre (6.8%), vitamins (A, B, C, E, K), essential nutrients phytochemicals (flavonoids, tannins, saponins, phenolics, and alkaloid), antioxidants (lycopene, beta-carotene, etc.). Its oil content is about 15% (Fulgoni et al., 2013) of which 71% monounsaturated fatty acid (MUFA), 13% PUFA and 16% SFA which are essential in promoting healthy blood and facilitate the bioavailability of fat-soluble vitamins and phytochemicals (Dreher and Davenport, 2013).

Avocado Waste Profile

While avocado is widely consumed as fresh fruit, packaged slices or pieces, it has also been processed industrially into many products such as oil, guacamole, jams, juice, chutney, sandwich spreads, sauces etc. (Rodriguez-Martinez et al., 2022; Merino et al., 2021). The processing of avocado into all these products (especially oil and guacamole) generate massive waste along the way, which are mainly peels, seeds and avocado pomace, and also inclusive of waste generated by pruning activities (Garcia-Vargas et al., 2020). The peels and seeds constitute about 21 – 30% of the fresh fruit weight (Rodriguez-Martinez et al., 2022), and in 2019 about 2 million of peels and seeds were generated as waste. This therefore, created a massive environmental issue of how to effectively dispose or manage it without impacting the environment negatively. It is at this point that waste valorization becomes a best alternative way of managing the waste by converting this waste into value-added bioproducts (Otlés and Kartal, 2018). This approach is one of the key components of circular economy, which focuses on process and resource efficiency, waste reduction, recycling and reusing (valorization)

The waste generated from oil extraction or guacamole processing can vary between 21 – 76%, and the waste has been estimated to constitute about 15% pomace, 45% wastewater, 27% peels and seeds, and 5% residual water (Permal et al., 2020). The wastewater is mostly generated during the cold pressing of avocado to extract oil. Permal et al. (2020)

reported that cold pressing method of extracting oil from avocado generates approximately 92% by-product (waste). These wastes are rich source of carbohydrate such as starch, cellulose, hemicellulose, pectin and excellent source of bioactive compounds (e.g., phenolic acids, catechins, flavonoids and procyanidins) with high antioxidant activity (Merino et al., 2021), and can therefore be utilized for the production of value-added products/ingredients as platform materials for the food, pharmaceuticals and cosmetics industries (Araujo et al., 2018). This strategic approach to agri-food waste management through valorization of avocado waste will help facilitate agri-food system sustainability and economic profitability.

Valorization of Avocado wastewater

The largest by-product (waste) of cold pressed avocado oil (CPAO) is the avocado wastewater and constitutes 45% of the total waste generated (Permal et al., 2020). Commercially, avocado oil has been extracted through chemical, mechanical and cold pressing extraction methods (see figure 1). However, cold pressing method has been the most preferable method because of its appealing emerald colour, buttery flavour, oleic acid and phytochemicals contents (carotenoids, tocopherol, etc.), and high smoking point of over 250 °C (Woolf et al., 2009; Permal et al., 2020). Disposal of avocado wastewater has been a concern for the industry because of the high disposal costs. Therefore, the best way to manage the disposal is to convert it to a value-added product. This can be achieved by spray drying to generate avocado wastewater powder which is use as bioantioxidant (Permal et al., 2020).

Figure 1: Various methods of extracting oil from avocado and the extraction process by-products (wastes). (Source: Garcia-Vargas et al., 2020)

The avocado wastewater is spray dried using whey protein concentrate (WPC) as carrier at 5% concentration, the AWW is fed into the drying chamber at feed rate of 5.8g/min. (commercial application will depend on the industrial spray dryer installed capacity for maximum efficiency – figure 2), and at inlet temperature of 180 °C. This is expected to have average yield of 49% AWW powder. The yield is calculated thus below;

$$\text{Yield \%} = \frac{\text{Power collected in cyclone (g)}}{\text{Mass of sample before spray drying}} \times 100$$

Figure 2: Conventional one-stage spray dryer (source: Samborska et al., 2022)

In the research conducted by Permal et al. (2020), it was found that addition of spray dried avocado wastewater powder into cooked pork fat was as effective as commonly used synthetic antioxidants (e.g., BHT, BHA, E316, etc.) in preventing lipid oxidation. The dried AWW powder containing active component of α -tocopherol and β -carotene, and can be alternatively used as antioxidant with the same effectiveness as commercially available synthetic antioxidants such as butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT), butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA), and sodium erythorbate (E316).

Valorization of Avocado peels and seeds

Avocado peels and seeds constitute about 27% waste generated from the avocado processing plant. They are rich in valuable component that can be extracted and be used as bioactive compounds e.g., catechin and quercetin, or processed into other product such as

bioethanol to be used as green fuel (Restrepo-Serna et al., 2022). Therefore, to optimize the complete valorization of these wastes, an integrated valorization of the wastes through biorefinery approach is considered more beneficial and commercially attractive (see figure 3). This biorefinery approach consist of extraction processes and post-extraction solid valorization, and process steps of Supercritical Fluid Extraction, ethanol production and cogeneration. And as reported by Restrepo-Serna et al. (2022) integrated biorefining of avocado peel and seed has shown to offer 43.05% and 47.41% profit margins respectively.

SFE is the first stage of the process which provides the bioactive compounds from the waste, and the residues from the first stage is further processed into ethanol which is also sent back to the first stage as co-solvent during the extraction process. The third stage of the process involves the gasification of the solid residue to generate syngas, a cogeneration process where the gas is passed through a turbine to generate steam and provide energy.

Figure 3: Process simulation of avocado waste valorization through Integrated biorefinery. (Source: Restrepo-Serna et al., 2022)

Supercritical Fluid Extraction (SFE) is an alternative technology for the efficient extraction of biocompounds from food biomass using clean and green technology, and is receiving more recognition than traditional methods of maceration and solvent extraction (del

Sanchez-Camargo et al., 2019). The main goal of the SFE is to extract catechin and quercetin from avocado seeds and peels respectively. The post-extraction residues of SFE extraction consist of polysaccharides such as starch, Cellulose and Hemicellulose, and these are then further processed into biomaterials, biochemicals, biofuels, etc. To start off, the avocado waste is milled to a particle size of 0.4mm while CO₂ is used as a supercritical solvent (possesses both gas and liquid properties) at operating temperature of 80 °C (see figure 5) and working pressure of 250 bar (Restrepo-Serna et al., 2022). The supercritical CO₂ is non-toxic, non-flammable, chemically inert, and of low-cost at the highest purity level (Sapkale et al., 2010). This extraction process is done with the use of ethanol as co-solvent, and with an extraction residence time of 30 mins.

Figure 4: Block diagram for the integrated utilization of avocado residues (source: Restrepo-Serna et al., 2022)

Figure 5: Avocado residue SFE flowsheet (Source: Restrepo-Serna et al., 2022)

Ethanol production from the avocado seed waste is carried out by subjecting the exhausted solid residue from the SFE process to gelatinization process at temperature of 63 °C, and then treated with α -amylase for liquefaction and amyloglucosidase to convert the starch substrate into a fermentable sugar (Glucose). The glucose obtained from the enzymatic hydrolysis is concentrated 20% w/v. The solution is then sent to a fermenter or bioreactor and pitch with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* for the fermentation of the glucose solution into ethanol. This is further purified by distillation and rectification process, and can further be concentrated up to 99.5% concentration (see figure 6).

Figure 6: Ethanol production flow sheet from the exhausted solid obtained in the avocado seed SFE. (Source: Restrepo-Serna et al., 2022)

Ethanol production from the avocado peel waste is carried out by pretreating the residue with sulfuric acid at 2% concentration and at temperature of 122 °C. The resulting liquid is then detoxified with calcium hydroxide at 60 °C, and this pretreatment produces xylose liquor. The remaining solid portion (cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin) is subjected to enzymatic hydrolysis using cellulases with a charge of 5% w/v at 50 °C. The remaining solid after this is removed by filtration which is mostly lignin. The liquid mixture of glucose liquor and xylose liquor is concentrated and fermented with recombinant bacterium *Z. mobilis* to produce ethanol from the mixture at a temperature of 30 °C. This resulting ethanol is further

purified by distillation and rectification process, and further concentrated up to 99.5% concentration (see figure 7).

Figure 7: Ethanol production flow sheet from the exhausted solid obtained in the avocado peel SFE. (Source: Restrepo-Serna et al., 2022)

The cogeneration is carried out through the gasification of the exhausted solid from ethanol production. Gasification is a partial oxidation process involving conversion of biomass at higher temperature (800 – 1200 °C) into a gaseous fuel or synthesis gas (syngas). It is an endothermic process which takes place in the presence of gasifying agents such as steam, air and oxygen (Patra et al., 2022). For this operation, the gasification is done at 30 bar pressure and with air used as gasifying agent fed at molar ratio of 1.2 to the exhausted solid. The main products of the process are CO, CO₂, CH₄, H₂S, and NH₃(syngas). The syngas is then passed through the turbine to take advantage of its high energy value. The resulting energy is utilized as energy source for the SFE process.

Conclusion

This integrated approach to valorization of avocado wastes offers more value-added products and better cost optimization when compared to treating these wastes outside the integrated biorefinery system. It facilitates lower production/operation cost and higher profit margins.

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